

Possible Antiamoebic Agents. Part XVIII. Mannich Base Dihydrochlorides of Substituted Quinazolines

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Twenty five new Mannich base dihydrochlorides of substituted-2-methyl-4-hydroxyquinazolines have been prepared with a view to testing their antiamoebic activity.

Several quinoline derivatives, like enterovioform, chloroquin and camcquin, and isoquinoline derivatives, like emetine, are well known amoebicides. Recently¹ some pyrimidines and dipyrimidines have also been found to possess antiamoebic activity *in vitro*.

The activity of chloroquin and camcquin is attributed to the basic side chain present in the molecules, whereas the activity of enterovioform and other oxine derivatives is reported to the formation of chelates of the drug with traces of essential elements (like Fe and Co) forming toxic complexes².

The quinazoline nucleus may be considered as a derivative of quinoline, isoquinoline or pyrimidine and as such the introduction of a hydroxy group in the *ortho* position to one ring nitrogen in a quinazoline, as in structure (I) should bring about chelation and the presence of an additional basic side chain should enhance its antiamoebic activity.

In the present investigation, the preparation of a number of substituted 4-hydroxyquinazolines with basic alkylamino side chain (I) has been undertaken with a view to studying their antiamoebic activity.

The required substituted 4-hydroxy-2-methylquinazolines were prepared by a modified v. Niementowski reaction³. This reaction, however, furnishes good yields only with formamide. With acetamide the yields of 2-methyl-4-hydroxyquinazolines⁴

1. Waletzky *et al.*, *Science* 1950, 111, 720; Janes *et al.*, *Brit. J. Pharm.*, 1952, 7, 486; *Chem. Abs.*, 1961, 65, 6506.
2. Albert *et al.*, *Med. J. Aust.*, 1944, 31, 245; *Brit. J. Expt. Path.*, 1947, 28, 69.
3. *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1895, ii, 51, 564.
4. Mayer and Wagner, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1943, 8, 235.

are 35-40%. By employing thio-acetamide in place of acetamide and carrying the reaction at 145-60°, the evolution of a molecule each of hydrogen sulphide and water took place readily and substituted-2-methyl-4-hydroxyquinazolines were obtained in excellent yields (75-98%).

Mannich base dihydrochlorides of the substituted-2-methyl-4-hydroxyquinazolines were obtained in the usual way by refluxing the appropriate quinazoline, the amine or amine hydrochloride, and paraformaldehyde (0.01 *M* each) in absolute ethanol (25 ml.), saturated with HCl-gas, for 8-10 hours on a waterbath. The crystals separating on cooling were filtered and recrystallised from ethanol. These were characterized through their picrates.

EXPERIMENTAL

5-Bromo-anthranilic Acid was prepared according to Wheeler *et al.*⁵.

5-Iodo-anthranilic Acid was prepared by reported method⁶.

3,5-Dichloroanthranilic Acid was prepared by method of Durrans⁷ using sulphuryl chloride (0.3*M*) and anthranilic acid (0.1*M*); 80% yield was obtained.

3,5-Di-iodoanthranilic Acid was prepared according to Wheeler *et al.*⁸.

Substituted-2-Methyl-4-hydroxyquinazolines.—A mixture of substituted anthranilic acid (0.1*M*), and thioacetamide (0.2*M*) was heated in an oil bath at 135-45° for 2 hrs. and then at 150-60° for another 30 minutes. Hydrogen sulfide was evolved. The solid residue was filtered, washed with 1% sodium bicarbonate solution and with water, and finally recrystallized from ethanol or acetic acid.

Hydrochlorides of these compounds were prepared by the action of dry HCl gas to an ethanolic solution of the substituted quinazoline and then refluxing it for 1 hour on a water bath. The separated crystals were filtered and recrystallised from ethanol. Picrates of these compounds were prepared as usual and recrystallised from ethanol.

The yields, m.p.'s and analyses of the substituted quinazolines, their hydrochlorides and picrates are recorded in Table I.

Mannich Base Dihydrochlorides of Substituted 2-Methyl-4-hydroxyquinazolines.—These compounds were obtained in the usual way. A mixture of the appropriate quinazoline, the amine or amine hydrochloride and paraformaldehyde (0.01*M* each) in absolute ethanol (25 ml) was refluxed on a water bath for 8-10 hours after saturating it with dry HCl gas. The crystals separating on cooling were filtered and recrystallised from ethanol.

5. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, **32**, 770.

6. *Org. Synthesis, Coll. Vol.*, 2, 1943, p. 349.

7. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, **123**, 1426.

8. *Amer. Chem. J.*, 1921, **34**, 405.

TABLE I

No.	R ₁	R ₂	% Yield	M.P.	% Nitrogen	
					Found.	Reqd.
1.	H	H	98	232°	..	..
2.	Br	H	88	302°	..	..
3.	I	H	86	345°	9.76	9.70
4.	Cl	Cl	80	> 360°	12.14	12.17
5.	I	I	75	> 360°	6.77	6.70

No.	M.P.	Picrates		M.P. °C	Hydrochlorides	
		Formula	% Nitrogen Found. Reqd.		Formula.	% Nitrogen Found. Reqd.
1.	..	..	..	..	..	..
2.	..	..	..	..	..	..
3.	256	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ O ₈ N ₃ I	13.62 13.50	> 360	C ₉ H ₈ ON ₂ Cl I	8.64 8.66
4.	238	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₈ N ₃ Cl ₂	15.20 15.25	> 360	C ₉ H ₇ ON ₂ Cl ₂	10.48 10.52
5.	274	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₈ N ₃ I ₂	10.88 10.92	> 360	C ₉ H ₇ ON ₂ ClI ₂	6.20 6.25

Picrates of these compounds were prepared as usual and were recrystallised from ethanol.

The m.p.'s, yields and analyses of these mannich base dihydrochlorides and their picrates are recorded in Table II (p. 371-72).

One of the authors (S. K. G.) wishes to express his obligation to Director General, C.S.I.R., for the award of a fellowship.

TABLE II

(Vide structure I)

No.	R ₁ , R ₂		% Yield	M.P.	Formula	% Nitrogen		Picrates		% Nitrogen	
						Found.	Reqd.	M. P.	Formula	Found.	Reqd.
1.	H H	-N(CH ₃) ₂	65	283°	C ₁₂ H ₁₇ ON ₃ Cl ₂	14.42	14.48	203°	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ O ₈ N ₆	18.80	18.83
2.	H H	-N(C ₂ H ₅) ₂	68	200°	C ₁₄ H ₂₁ ON ₃ Cl ₂	13.16	13.20	198°	C ₂₀ H ₂₃ O ₈ N ₆	17.70	17.72
3.	H H	-N	73	323°	C ₁₃ H ₂₁ ON ₃ Cl ₂	12.64	12.72	205°	C ₂₁ H ₂₅ O ₈ N ₆	17.27	17.28
4.	H H	-N	90	*346°	C ₁₄ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₃ Cl ₂	12.62	12.65	204°	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ O ₈ N ₆	17.23	17.21
5.	Br H	-N(CH ₃) ₂	58	314°	C ₁₂ H ₁₆ ON ₃ Cl ₂ Br	11.32	11.38	186°	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ O ₈ N ₆ Br	16.02	16.00
6.	Br H	-N	62	*352°	C ₁₄ H ₁₉ ON ₃ Cl ₂ Br	10.60	10.63	199°	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₈ N ₆ Br	15.25	15.24
7.	I H	-NH.C ₂ H ₅ .C ₆ H ₅	48	298°	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ ON ₃ Cl ₂ I	8.68	8.74	212°	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ O ₈ N ₆ I	13.28	13.24
8.	I H	-NH-CH ₃	50	300°	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ ON ₃ Cl ₂ I	10.40	10.44	223°	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ O ₈ N ₆ I	15.10	15.05
9.	I H	-NH	58	320°	C ₁₆ H ₂₀ ON ₃ Cl ₂ I	8.90	8.93	240°	C ₂₂ H ₂₃ O ₈ N ₆ I	13.43	13.41
10.	I H	-NH.C ₂ H ₅	46	340°	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ ON ₃ Cl ₂ I	10.00	10.08	230°	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ O ₈ N ₆ I	14.65	14.68
11.	I H	-N(CH ₃) ₂	55	345°	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ ON ₃ Cl ₂ I	10.02	10.90	238°	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ O ₈ N ₆ I	14.62	14.68
12.	I H	-N(C ₂ H ₅) ₂	48	298°	C ₁₄ H ₂₀ ON ₃ Cl ₂ I	9.50	9.45	*260°	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ O ₈ N ₆ I	14.04	14.00
13.	I H	-N	40	330°	C ₁₃ H ₂₀ ON ₃ Cl ₂ I	9.30	9.21	276°	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ O ₈ N ₆ I	13.64	13.72
14.	I H	-N	53	*335°	C ₁₄ H ₁₈ O ₂ N ₃ Cl ₂ I	9.20	9.17	*264°	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₈ N ₆ I	13.65	13.68

TABLE II (contd.)

No.	R ₁	R ₂		% Yield	M.P.	Formula	% Nitrogen Found.	% Nitrogen Reqd.	M.P.	Ficrates Formula	% Nitrogen Found.	% Nitrogen Reqd.
15.	Cl	Cl	-NH.CH ₃	38	*288°	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ ON ₃ Cl ₄	12.20	12.17	109°	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₈ N ₆ Cl ₂	16.77	16.76
16.	Cl	Cl	-NH.C ₆ H ₅	40	278°	C ₁₂ H ₁₅ ON ₃ Cl ₄	11.01	11.94	178°	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₈ N ₆ Cl ₂	16.33	16.31
17.	Cl	Cl	-NH-	52	315°	C ₁₆ H ₂₁ ON ₃ Cl ₄	10.19	10.16	184°	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ O ₈ N ₆ Cl ₂	14.70	14.76
18.	Cl	Cl	-N(CH ₃) ₂	52	354°	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ ON ₃ Cl ₄	11.08	11.94	210°	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₈ N ₆ Cl ₂	16.35	16.31
19.	Cl	Cl	-N(C ₆ H ₅) ₂	45	*300°	C ₁₄ H ₁₉ ON ₃ Cl ₄	10.83	10.85	226°	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ O ₈ N ₆ Cl ₂	15.43	15.48
20.	Cl	Cl	-N-	60	*360°	C ₁₃ H ₁₉ ON ₃ Cl ₄	10.50	10.52	240°	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ O ₈ N ₆ Cl ₂	16.17	15.13
21.	Cl	Cl	-N-	60	*357°	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₃ Cl ₄	10.46	10.47	*258°	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ O ₈ N ₆ Cl ₂	15.12	15.09
22.	I	I	-NH.CH ₃	38	> 360°	O ₁₁ H ₁₃ ON ₃ Cl ₂ I ₂	7.91	7.95	209°	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₈ N ₆ I	12.21	12.38
23.	I	I	-N(CH ₃) ₂	37	> 360°	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ ON ₃ Cl ₂ I ₂	7.75	7.76	232°	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₈ N ₆ I ₂	12.00	12.03
24.	I	I	-N-	48	> 060°	C ₁₃ H ₁₉ ON ₃ Cl ₂ I ₂	7.50	7.51	*275°	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ O ₈ N ₆ I ₂	11.30	11.38
25.	I	I	-N-	60	> 360°	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₃ Cl ₂ I ₂	7.50	7.19	*200°	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ O ₈ N ₆ I ₂	11.31	11.35

*Melts with decomposition